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Challenges for transboundary management of a European brown bear population

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Abstract

Pan-European legislation stimulates international cooperation to overarching challenges of large carnivore management across jurisdictions. We present an analysis for current transboundary brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) population management in Croatia and Slovenia. Slovenia's bear management attempts aimed to reduce human-bear conflicts, by limiting the size and distribution of the bear population, with a relatively frequent use of intervention shooting. In contrast, fewer conflicts occur in Croatia and bears have been traditionally managed as a valuable game species, with heavily male-biased trophy hunting. On average 9% of the estimated bear population was removed annually in Croatia and 18% in Slovenia for the years 2005-2010. In Croatia, a greater proportion of adult males were shot than in Slovenia (80% vs 47% of total hunted males, respectively). We model a scenario for the shared panmictic population and two scenarios assuming that Croatian and Slovenian bear populations were spatially closed. When isolated, each countries' policies lead to potentially undesired management directions. The Slovenian bear population showed a stable or slightly decreasing trend that maintained its sex and age structure, while the Croatian bear population showed an increase in size but with a possible lack of older male bear. The panmictic scenario showed that different management policies buffered each other out with the overall combined population trend being slightly increasing with a sustained age/sex structure. The recent geopolitical refugee crisis has led to the partial erection of border security fencing between the two countries. Our data illustrate how the impacts of constructed fencing put in place to address border security issues may also impact the fate of Europe's bear populations and other wildlife species that use shared ecosystems.

Keywords: brown bear (*Ursus arctos*), Croatia, Slovenia, modelling, population dynamics, transboundary management

43
44 **Data Availability:** All relevant data are uploaded as Supplemental files (A, B, C, D and E) to
45 the manuscript and available on Mendeley Data repository.

46 **Ethics:** On October 17, 2012, Committee on Veterinary Ethics at the Faculty of Veterinary
47 Medicine, University of Zagreb, Croatia issued confirmation letter (Klasa: 640-01/12-17/3; Ur. br.:
48 251-61-01/139-12-19) about ethical acceptability and scientific justification in performing sample and
49 data collection for the production of this manuscript.

50 **Competing interests:** The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

51 1. Introduction

52 Managing large carnivores such as brown bears (*Ursus arctos*) represents one of the greatest
53 challenges in biodiversity conservation. This challenge is tied to the nutrient requirements of their
54 large body size and their trophic position requires that individuals need very large home ranges [1].
55 As a consequence, many large carnivore populations function on scales measured in thousands or
56 tens of thousands of square kilometres. In a world where the human footprint is constantly
57 expanding [2], and available areas of interconnected habitat are shrinking, this can represent
58 considerable management challenges. In addition to the ecological demands posed by their spatial
59 requirements, there is also a range of issues related to the administrative and political fragmentation
60 of the landscape as individual movements and population distribution areas will inevitably cross
61 multiple jurisdictions. This is especially acute in Europe where countries are relatively small, and
62 where a high degree of autonomy for environmental issues is often further delegated to sub-national
63 levels like cantons, states, regions, counties, provinces, municipalities and protected area
64 administrations. As a result, European populations of species like brown bears stretch across multiple
65 jurisdictional borders. Of the ten brown bear populations in Europe, eight of them span international
66 boundaries, with two spanning four countries and one even spanning a total of nine countries [3].

67 There is also a range of social, cultural, political, institutional and economic issues that
68 complicate management. Large carnivores often attract very polarized points of view among the
69 public, and as a result, are embroiled in a diverse range of conflicts that include complex interactions
70 between economic and social elements [4]. As these elements vary between regions and countries in
71 line with differences in ecological and socio-economic conditions it can make achieving
72 transboundary cooperation in management very difficult. Although Pan-European bodies of
73 legislation like the European Union's Habitats Directive and the Council of Europe's Bern Convention
74 aim to stimulate international cooperation in biodiversity conservation [5,6,7] there has actually
75 been very little progress in achieving such formalized coordination at any level beyond cooperation
76 between scientists in research and monitoring [8] in the case of large carnivores. This is despite
77 recent analyses which have conceptually [9] and empirically demonstrated the importance of
78 transboundary coordination, for example in the field of population monitoring [10,11] and comparing
79 divergent management approaches impact shared populations [12,13]. Although there is widespread
80 experience in Europe with transboundary cooperation in protected area management [14]. It would
81 appear that the social and political complexity is a major hindrance towards achieving the much-
82 needed cross-border cooperation of managing controversial species like large carnivores [9].

83 In this study, we present an analysis of brown bear hunting management in Slovenia and
84 Croatia, two countries that share the north-western part of the Dinaric-Pindos bear population of
85 south-eastern Europe. Although both countries have a shared history from the former Yugoslavia
86 era, their independence since 1991 and in minor measure different entry dates (Slovenia 2004,
87 Croatia 2013) into the European Union has led to very different bear management regimes in more
88 recent times. Previous work has focused on either one or the other national segments
89 [15,16,17,18,19] but no studies have yet combined data from both sides of the shared border into a
90 common analysis framework. We first describe how bears are hunted in both countries with respect
91 to hunting rates and age and sex categories of the harvest. We then model the impacts of these

92 harvest management strategies under 3 hypothetical scenarios of each country's portion of the
93 population being either connected or closed.

94 When this study was initiated the scenarios involving closure seemed rather abstract as there
95 were no serious obstacles to animal movement across the border. However, recent geopolitical
96 developments (the refugee crisis of 2015) have led to the erection of border security fencing
97 between the two countries [20,21]. Although this fencing was designed to stem the flow of refugees
98 it could also impact bear movements. Our dataset does not permit the assessment of these fences
99 impact on bear movements, but our findings do have important relevance to bear conservation in
100 these areas. The goal was to illustrate the impacts of two different management systems and the
101 border fence as a potential absolute barrier to the population connectivity and the need for
102 transnational cooperation, rather than to directly critique the management practices in either of the
103 two countries.

104 2. Study area

105 The Dinaric-Pindos Mountains extend from Slovenia in the north, southwards through
106 Croatia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Montenegro, Serbia, Kosovo, Albania, the Former Yugoslav Republic
107 of Macedonia and Greece. The overall Dinaric-Pindos population size of brown bears in 2014 was in
108 the order of 3000 individuals, making it the second largest in Europe [3]. Although Slovenia
109 represents the northernmost tip of this large population, it represents the crucial linkage to the
110 highly threatened population in the Alps [22]. The bear population was greatly reduced by the late
111 19th and early 20th centuries. However, protective legislation was imposed in the 1930s in each
112 country, and these policies were continued through the Yugoslavia era when the countries were
113 united [23,24,25]. Following periods of protection, carefully regulated hunting was initiated, under
114 which the bear populations continued to grow. When the countries separated again in 1991, they
115 continued to harvest bears, although their policies began to diverge. Slovenia's bear management
116 aimed to reduce human-bear conflicts (by limiting the size and distribution of the bear population) to
117 a far greater degree than Croatia's policy which focused more on managing for trophy hunting
118 [16,17]. This was in part due to Slovenia's earlier EU membership which only permits bear culling
119 under derogations from Habitats Directive in response to conflict, but also due to a higher level of
120 conflicts with land uses like sheep farming that has been heavily promoted by subsidies paid through
121 the EU Common Agricultural Policy after Slovenia joining the EU [26]. Conflict levels in Croatia are
122 much lower [27]. Slovenia's current bear range (c. 4000 km²) borders directly onto Croatia's bear
123 range (c. 10 000 km²), which in turn is contiguous with that in Bosnia & Herzegovina.

124 3. Materials and Methods

125 3.1. Data collection

126 We used registered brown bear removal data from both Croatia and Slovenia (Supplemental
127 file B), covering the six-year period from 2005-2010. The removal data consists of all causes of bear
128 mortality as well as cases of taking out the live animals from the population. Once a live animal is
129 taken out from the population it is considered dead for that population. The dataset included: (1)
130 identification number of each bear, (2) cause of removal from the population, (3) date of the event,
131 (4) coordinates of sites where removal occurred, (5) sex, and (6) age of each animal. The age of each
132 removed animal was determined by one of two methods. For most bears, age was determined by
133 counting the cementum annuli in teeth [28,29] done by Matson's Laboratory LLC, Montana, USA. The
134 second method for ageing was developed by Jerina [30] for the bears that could not be aged using
135 teeth sections, for example, if no teeth were available. The method predicts age based on other
136 information (bear pelt, body weight and other measurements) using regression trees, e.g. [18]. For

137 Croatia (total n=535) and Slovenia (total n=614) respectively, 412 and 518 bears ages were
 138 determined based on cementum annuli method and 110 and 96 bears were aged using Jerina's
 139 method, while 13 and 8 bears remained without age determination. Each case of brown bear
 140 removal was recorded according to protocols established in the respective country [16,31]. We have
 141 reason to believe that the available material provides a relatively complete picture of legal and
 142 accidental anthropogenic mortality.

143 For each bear, the cause of removal from the population was categorized into one of four
 144 categories. "Harvest quota" included animals killed within prescribed legal hunting seasons each
 145 year. "Intervention shooting" encompassed all cases of killing problem bears and/or bears that
 146 appeared outside of predetermined acceptable bear zones. The category "Traffic kill" included all
 147 cases of deaths due to train and road vehicle collisions with bears. The "Other causes" category
 148 included all other causes of bear removals that could not be placed in one of the first three
 149 categories. It comprised: natural deaths, illegal killings (e.g. poisoning [32]), undetermined causes,
 150 accidental and indirect causes of anthropogenic mortality (e.g. drowning in a water well) as well as
 151 taking out the live animals from the wild population (orphaned cubs rescued and sent to Kuterevo
 152 bear sanctuary, or adults live-captured for augmentation of other bear populations, e.g. in Italy [33]).

153 We measured distances of all bear removal locations from the administrative border
 154 between the two countries using the tool "Near" in ArcMap (ESRI). Considering average home range
 155 diameters for females to be 21.5 km and for males 40.9 km [34,35,16], we determined if a given
 156 removal was within a home range diameter from the border.

157 In addition to bear removal datasets, we used data compiled from regular observations of
 158 bears on feeding sites to estimate litter sizes and survival probabilities for cubs of the year (COY) in
 159 both countries (Supplemental file C). For Croatia, we used data from 2007-2011, and for Slovenia
 160 from 2004-2010. Observations were made two times a year in Croatia (April and October [31]) and
 161 three times a year in Slovenia (May, August and October [36]). Data were gathered from 120 sites in
 162 Croatia and 167 sites in Slovenia.

163 3.2. Statistical analysis

164 All statistical analyses were conducted in R 3.0.3 [37]. To test for differences between
 165 proportions we used Two-sample tests for equality of proportions with continuity correction
 166 ("prop.test" function [38]). When testing for differences between two arithmetic means we used the
 167 Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction ("wilcox.test" function) when variances between
 168 two means were not significantly different or by fitting generalized linear model (GLM) and
 169 performing analysis of deviance ("anova" function) when variances were different. Homogeneity and
 170 differences between variances of arithmetic means were tested using the Fligner-Killeen test of
 171 homogeneity of variances ("fligner.test" function [38]). For count data, we used Poisson or quasi-
 172 Poisson (if overdispersion occurred) distribution of errors and for proportion data binomial
 173 distribution of errors.

174 3.3. Matrix model parameterization

175 To investigate the consequences of the current hunting regimes, and to explore a set of
 176 contrasting scenarios, we constructed a two-sex, age-classified, density-independent deterministic
 177 Leslie matrix model assuming post-breeding census [38,39,40,41]. A general density-independent
 178 matrix population model can be written as:

$$179 \quad N_{t+1} = \mathbf{A} * N_t \quad (\text{Eq. 1}),$$

180 where the vector N_t is the number of individuals in the different age and sex classes at time
 181 t , and \mathbf{A} is the (density independent) transition matrix [40], with total population size n_t being the
 182 sum of all age and sex classes across N_t . In our two-sex model, we assumed that all bears died after
 183 the age of 20 years, thus distributing males and females respectively across 21 age classes. The

184 transition matrix **A** was parameterized based on demographic rates given in the Supplemental file A,
185 Table A1.

186 As a first step, we ran 1000 simulations of this transition matrix to estimate a stable sex and
187 age structure (42 classes in total) for a fictive non-hunted bear population using the add-on library
188 “popbio” [43] in R, applying the “eigen.analysis” function. Given the sex and age structure, we
189 adjusted according to the actual proportions of females and males in the Slovenian part of the
190 population [42]. For the Croatian part, we didn’t have sound estimates of female:male ratio in the
191 population and we wanted to have the same initial sex structure ratios so the effects of modelling
192 would be comparable. A population vector N_0 then was established by distributing the population
193 size n_0 proportionally across 42 classes from the simulated and adjusted non-hunted age and sex
194 structure.

195 After establishing a stable initial non-hunted population structure our next step was to
196 implement hunting mortality, based on registered data in both countries for the period 2005-2010.
197 The average annual hunting mortality (H_t) vector was comprised of female and male hunting
198 mortality for each age class (42 integers) and divided by a number of data collection years ($n_y=6$). H_t
199 vectors were formed for both countries separately and combined. These vectors were used to test
200 various scenarios.

$$201 \quad H_t = \frac{(H_f + H_m)}{n_y} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

202 H_t was subtracted from the population vector N , in order to obtain estimates of the post-
203 hunting population size and sex and age structure. Hunting mortality was expressed as real numbers
204 and assumed being constant across 5-year iterations (n.years) of the simulated population’s
205 development. In cases where results of subtraction for particular sex and age classes were below
206 zero, final values in the subtracted vector were transformed to 0. These cases could appear in older
207 age classes which were represented as a minor proportions in the total population size. We
208 simulated 1000 iterations of the process and recorded population size and structure after each
209 iteration of 5 years.

210 The matrix model was used to forecast the population development regarding the
211 differences in management practices in terms of total size, and sex and age structure in Croatia and
212 Slovenia. The importance of using hypothetical scenarios is to understand how differences in
213 management between the two countries combined with potential effects of a border fence may
214 affect the population and which parameters are most influential in driving the differences in
215 projections. In the first scenario, we assumed closed but shared panmictic Croato-Slovenian brown
216 bear population. This scenario served as a baseline for comparison and represented the period
217 before the border fence was erected. In the second and third scenario, we assumed that the Croatian
218 and Slovenian bear populations were separated and closed, i.e. with no migration or dispersal of
219 bears across the borders, corresponding to a “reality” where the border fence became an absolute
220 barrier. We also tested what would be the minimum population size that would be sustainable ($\lambda=1$,
221 reproductive female:male ratio less than 6:1) with an implementation of the current management
222 practices in Croatia and Slovenia conjointly. The results of each scenario were summarized through
223 three output metrics: the overall population growth rate (λ), differences in the reproductive
224 female:male sex ratio (reproductive female proportion), and the sex and age structure’s deviation
225 from the initial population. Reproductive female:male sex ratios were obtained by summing the final
226 frequencies for all reproductive age classes separately for females and males. As a maximum ratio of
227 reproductive females and males that would not affect population growth because of the lack of the
228 males in the population we took 6:1, based on the assumption that one male can on average
229 successfully mate with a maximum of 6 females in one mating season [44].

230 Average annual lambda for each of 1000 iterations at the end of 5-years period (n.years) was
231 approximated according to the equation where n denotes population size:

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{n_{n.years}}{n_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{n.years}} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

233 3.4. Sensitivity analysis

234 The sensitivity analysis [45] is a standard procedure to acquire the impact (positive or
 235 negative) of implemented demographic parameters in the model to the variable of interest
 236 (population size and average lambda in our case). To run it, we developed a new matrix model which
 237 used sex and age composition results obtained by the matrix model for initial population structure.
 238 For each of the 16 parameters tested (Table 3), we set an arbitrary minimum and maximum value
 239 and run the model for 1000 simulations. From the results gained for each parameter, we took values
 240 of 2nd and 4th quantiles as a minimum and maximum range values, respectively. We standardized
 241 results for each parameter to be directly comparable. Then we tested the correlation of the
 242 parameters with two variables, final population size and population growth rate (lambda) by setting
 243 two GLMs, one for each explanatory variable. The final model was run for 10000 simulations.

244 Scripts, for free software environment for statistical computing and graphics “R”, to perform
 245 described modelling process and model sensitivity analyses can be found in Supplemental files D and
 246 E.

247 4. Results

248 4.1. Removals and hunting quotas

249 A total of 535 bears were removed in Croatia and 614 in Slovenia during the six-year period
 250 from 2005 until 2010. Total removal included both quota hunting and recorded removals due to all
 251 other causes. On average 89 bears per year were removed in Croatia and 102 in Slovenia, and there
 252 was a higher (χ -sq.=28.43, df=1, $p < 0.0001$) mean annual offtake in Slovenia (18.3% of the estimated
 253 population size) than in Croatia (8.9%) (Table 1). In addition, the quota filling (number of hunted
 254 bears relative to planned quota) was also (χ -sq.=142.35, df=1, $p < 0.0001$) higher in Slovenia (102.7%)
 255 than in Croatia (74.7%).

256
 257 **Table 1. Total annual brown bear removals, planned and filled harvest quota in Croatia and**
 258 **Slovenia from 2005 till 2010.**

Year	CROATIA				SLOVENIA			
	All removals	% of N	Planned quota ¹	Filled quota	All removals	% of N	Planned quota ¹	Filled quota
2005	51	5.1	80	31	95	17.0	67	73
2006	82	8.2	70	49	126	22.6	100	94
2007	58	5.8	70	50	108	19.4	100	89
2008	115	11.5	70	64	92	16.5	75	76
2009	109	10.9	100	86	85	15.2	70	70
2010	120	12.0	100	86	108	19.4	75	98
Total	535		490	366	614		487	500
Average		8.9				18.3		

259 N = estimated population size.

260 ¹Planned quota in Slovenia includes hunting mortality and intervention shooting of bears. In Croatia, it includes
 261 only hunting mortality.

262
 263 There was a significant difference between the two countries in the proportions of removals
 264 from the different categories (Anova; df=3, $p < 0.0001$; Figure 1). It was mainly caused by the
 265 difference in intervention shooting (Croatia 5.2% and Slovenia 16.6%; χ -sq.=35.77, df=1, $p < 0.0001$)

266 while there was no difference between the proportion of hunting mortality in Croatia and Slovenia
 267 (χ -sq.=1.47, df=1, p=0.23). However, combined hunting mortality and intervention shooting, which
 268 together represent intentional human-caused killing, was a more frequent cause of mortality in
 269 Slovenia than in Croatia (Croatia 73.4% and Slovenia 81.3%; χ -sq.=9.60, df=1, p<0.01). There was also
 270 a difference between mortality from traffic accidents and removals from other causes, but to a lesser
 271 extent than for intervention shooting (χ -sq.=4.02, df=1, p<0.05, and χ -sq.=5.18, df=1, p<0.05,
 272 respectively). Both causes were more frequent in Croatia.
 273

274
 275 **Figure 1. Proportions of four different causes of reported removals in Croatia and Slovenia.**
 276

277 4.2. Hunting bag composition

278 The proportions of male bears in hunting mortality was higher (χ -sq.=29.09, df=1,
 279 p<<0.0001) in Croatia (77%, n=365) than in Slovenia (59%, n=397; Figure 2). Within the hunted male
 280 category, the proportion of adult males over 3 years of age was also larger in Croatia, 80% (n=281)
 281 versus 47% (n=230) in Slovenia (χ -sq.=61.09, df=1, p<<0.0001). In contrast, there was no difference
 282 (χ -sq.=0.28, df=1, p=0.60) between the proportion of males removed in non-quota categories
 283 between Croatia (45% males, n=170) and Slovenia (48% males, n=217). The proportion of males in
 284 the total reported removals was higher (χ -sq.=16.81, df=1, p<<0.0001) in Croatia (67% males, n=535)
 285 than in Slovenia (55% males, n=614) as well.
 286

Figure 2. Sex and age structure of hunted brown bears in Croatia and Slovenia for 2005 – 2010 period.

We found a significant difference ($df=1127$, $p<<0.0001$) between the average age of all bears in the total reported removals in Croatia 4.4 ± 0.15 years (all means ± 1 SE, $n=522$) and in Slovenia 2.9 ± 0.12 years ($n=606$). There was also a difference ($df=754$, $p<<0.0001$) between the average age of bears shot in quota hunting in Croatia, 5.2 ± 0.17 years ($n=363$) and in Slovenia 3.1 ± 0.14 years ($n=392$). There was no difference ($W=15579.5$, $p=0.16$) between the average age of bears that died from all non-quota causes in Croatia 2.5 ± 0.22 years ($n=159$) and in Slovenia 2.5 ± 0.24 years ($n=214$), as well as ($W=4570$, $p=0.85$; $W=395.5$, $p=0.22$) between the average age of bears killed in traffic collisions and from other causes in Croatia (2.1 ± 0.24 years, $n=102$; 2.8 ± 0.68 years, $n=30$) and in Slovenia (2.9 ± 0.44 years, $n=91$; 3.3 ± 0.61 years, $n=22$), respectively. A difference was found ($W=575$, $p<<0.0001$) between the average age of bears shot in intervention shooting in Croatia 3.7 ± 0.38 years ($n=27$) and in Slovenia 2.0 ± 0.27 years ($n=101$). Furthermore, differences in average ages between different sexes in quota hunting and non-quota removals for each country and across countries were tested (Table 2).

Table 2. Average age between sexes in quota hunting and non-quota removals for each country and across countries.

	CROATIA		SLOVENIA		Comparison	
	Average age	n	Average age	n		
Quota	Females	5.3 ± 0.34	82	3.2 ± 0.24	161	$p<<0.0001^{***}$
	Males	5.2 ± 0.20	281	3.0 ± 0.16	230	$p<<0.0001^{***}$
	Comparison	$p=0.43$		$p=0.82$		
Non-quota	Females	3.1 ± 0.36	67	3.1 ± 0.38	105	$p=0.25$
	Males	2.1 ± 0.28	73	2.0 ± 0.28	102	$p=0.36$
	Comparison	$p<0.05^*$		$p<0.05^*$		

4.3. Spatial distribution of bear removals

On average, females and males were removed further away ($df=414$, $p<<0.0001$ and $df=692$, $p<<0.0001$) from the administrative state border (Figure 3A) in Croatia (32.9 ± 2.57 km, $n=152$ and 46.6 ± 2.15 km, $n=356$) than in Slovenia (15.7 ± 0.59 km, $n=263$ and 18.0 ± 0.63 km, $n=337$), respectively. The average distances of female removals from the administrative state border were shorter than for males in both countries (Croatia: $df=507$, $p<0.001$; Slovenia: $W=39949.5$, $p<0.05$). A total of 73% of removed females and 97% of males in Slovenia and 52% of females and 55% of males in Croatia were removed within their respective average female (21.5 km) and male (40.9 km) home range (HR) diameter from the state border (Figure 3B).

318
 319 **Figure 3A. Locations of all recorded bear removals in Croatia and Slovenia in the 2005-2010 period.**
 320 Males are marked with black circles and females with white triangles. Each grey-scaled zone
 321 represents distance increments of 10 km from the administrative border between countries.
 322

323
 324 **Figure 3B. Cumulative percentages of all bear removals in relation to the distance from the**
 325 **Croatian-Slovenian border.** Vertical lines refer to average female (21.5 km) and male (40.9 km) home
 326 range (HR) diameters.
 327

328 4.4. Scenario results for Croatia and Slovenia under conditions of 329 panmixia and isolation

330 When modelling a combined Croatian and Slovenian transboundary population (Figure A3)
 331 the model resulted in an increase in population size for about 25 % after 5 years with the average
 332 lambda value of $\lambda=1.046$ (95% distribution range 1.033-1.057, Figure 4). The initial proportion of
 333 reproductive females after 5 years changed from 62.8% to 70.5% ($\chi\text{-sq.}=11.41$, $df=1$, $p<0.001$) and
 334 the population structure (Table A3) showed differences from the initial state ($p<0.01$) but with no
 335 serious lack of older males in the population. The ratio of reproductive females and males was 2.4:1.

336 The minimum population size that would be sustainable regarding total number and sex and
 337 age structure of removed bears from the population, at the same rates as in the study period, was
 338 960 for a panmictic scenario. In this scenario, two conditions should be met: $\lambda=1$ and reproductive
 339 female:male ratio less than 6:1.

340
 341

Figure 4. Distribution of 1000 model run lambda values. Distribution in figure 4 is given for joint Croatian and Slovenian scenario (panmixia).

In the scenario where Croatia was modelled as a separate and closed country (Figure A4) after a 5-year modelling period, the population size increased by about one and a half times from the initial population size with an average population growth rate $\lambda=1.084$, (95% distribution range of predictions 1.071-1.097). The initial proportion of reproductive females after 5 years changed from 62.8% to 69.7% (χ -sq.=5.87, df=1, $p<0.05$) and the ratio of reproductive females and males was 2.3:1. Modelled population structure regarding sex and age categories showed significant differences from the initial population structure ($p<0.01$), especially with respect to a lack of males older than 10 years of age in the population. The closed Slovenian population scenario (Figure A5) showed a stable or slightly decreased population size after a 5-year period with an average lambda value of $\lambda=0.998$, (95% distribution range 0.985-1.010). The initial proportion of reproductive females after 5 years did not change significantly (from 62.7% to 70.7%; χ -sq.=3.72, df=1, $p=0.054$) and the population structure did not show the difference from the initial population structure ($p=0.75$). The ratio of reproductive females and males was 2.4:1.

4.5. Sensitivity analysis results

Among 16 tested parameters (Table 3) the highest positive impact on the final population size, in both countries combined and Croatia and Slovenia separately, was associated with initial population size (0.65-0.68) and litter size (0.35-0.38), followed by survival rates of adult females, female:male ratio, survival rate of COYs and survival rates of subadult females. Conversely, litter size (0.43-0.54) with a survival rate of adult females (0.38-0.44) had a major positive effect on the average population growth rate (λ). Female:male ratio, initial population size, the survival rate of COYs and survival rates of subadult females all had important positive effects on λ . The parameters with the highest negative impact on both, the final population size and λ , were the inter-litter interval (0.21-0.31) and the loss of the whole litters (0.20-0.29).

370 **Table 3. Results of sensitivity analyses run for 16 parameters used in the population matrix modelling for Croatia, Slovenia and both countries combined.**

Parameter	CROATIA		SLOVENIA		CROATIA+SLOVENIA	
	Population size in 5 years	Average λ	Population size in 5 years	Average λ	Population size in 5 years	Average λ
Whole litter loss	*-0.2101	*-0.2890	*-0.2016	*-0.2710	*-0.2004	*-0.2418
Interlitter interval	*-0.2332	*-0.3114	*-0.2307	*-0.2986	*-0.2082	*-0.2477
Survival rate of COYs	0.2110	0.2863	0.1960	0.2706	0.1905	0.2432
Survival rate of female yearlings	0.0725	0.1038	0.0702	0.0920	0.0675	0.0862
Survival rate of subadult females	0.2431	**0.3289	0.1836	0.2524	0.1823	0.2218
Survival rate of adult females	0.2758	**0.3897	**0.3059	**0.4422	0.2937	**0.3785
Survival rate of females at age of 20	-0.0016	0.0036	0.0104	0.0018	0.0006	0.0043
Survival rate of male yearlings	0.0337	0.0488	0.0266	0.0406	0.0254	0.0251
Survival rate of subadult males	0.0423	0.0664	0.0370	0.0544	0.0238	0.0220
Survival rate of adult males	0.0198	0.0335	0.0457	0.0699	0.0124	0.0203
Survival rate of males at age of 20	-0.0024	0.0002	-0.0038	0.0027	0.0029	0.0011
Litter size	**0.3862	**0.5359	**0.3751	**0.5110	**0.3489	**0.4301
Harvest rate	-0.0551	-0.0915	-0.0830	-0.1410	-0.1279	-0.1999
Initial population size	**0.6534	0.2034	**0.6645	**0.3010	**0.6759	**0.4354
Age of first reproduction	0.0463	0.0646	0.0392	0.0428	0.0321	0.0440
Female:male ratio	0.2294	**0.3143	0.2186	**0.3068	0.2658	**0.3785

**parameters with the most positive effect

*parameters with the most negative effect

372

5. Discussion

373 The data on brown bear management collected from Slovenia and Croatia demonstrates the
374 contrasting management regimes operating in these two countries. Slovenia operates with a higher
375 harvest rate, a higher degree of quota fulfilment, a far greater proportion of females and young
376 bears among those killed, and a relatively frequent use of intervention killing to remove nuisance
377 bears. Croatia's management regime has a lower harvest rate, lower degree of quota fulfilment, a
378 larger proportion of males and older animals in the bag, and a less frequent use of lethal control of
379 nuisance bears. Due to mentioned differences in management practices, the implemented hunting
380 mortality for each country differs and hence the model accordingly produced different outcomes.

381 Brown bears are listed on Annex IV of the Habitats Directive in all European Union countries
382 regardless of their population size. This designation requires "a strict protection" of the species.
383 Formally, the only deliberate killing of bears must, therefore, be done under a system of exceptions
384 called derogations. However, different countries apply widely different management practices and
385 interpretations. Lethal control, technically organized as a derogation from protection but largely
386 organized as a form of de facto hunting is practised in Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Slovenia and Croatia.
387 Countries like Slovakia and Bulgaria operate with a more restrictive form of hunter-based removal,
388 while Romania has currently imposed a stop on what was a de facto hunting system. It is therefore
389 not exceptional that different countries operate with different management systems. However, the
390 difference between Slovenia and Croatia is striking given the overall similarities of habitat and their
391 shared social, cultural and political history as part of Yugoslavia until relatively recently. Moreover,
392 both countries share a large proportion of the population due to the transboundary movement of
393 bears.

394 The major difference between the two countries appears to be in the extent to which bears
395 have become embroiled with conflicts [27]. Slovenia's earlier succession to the European Union
396 opened the way for access to agricultural subsidies that were used to stimulate sheep production in
397 bear habitats, initially without any requirements for protective measures. In addition to this
398 economic conflict, bear conflicts have also been instrumentalised in Slovenia as party political
399 symbols of wider socio-political divisions [26,46,47,48]. The combination of these processes led to
400 bears becoming more associated as a conflict species that led to a reduced tolerance for their
401 presence. Therefore, management practices have aimed to hold their numbers stable, and mainly
402 confine their distribution to a management "core" area along the southern border with Croatia [19].
403 In contrast, there are relatively few conflicts with brown bears in Croatia and they have been
404 traditionally managed as a valuable game species where the sales of hunting trophies have been a
405 major source of financial revenue for local hunting organizations [17,489]. Although bears are
406 excluded from certain areas (such as the islands and coastline), there have been no explicit efforts to
407 limit distribution or population growth, although it is felt that the bear population is at a level which
408 is suitable for the available habitat and for local tolerance [25,49].

409 Our modelling scenarios provided insights into the potential impacts of these different
410 policies. When viewed in isolation the two countries' policies lead to potentially unsatisfactory
411 management directions. The Slovenian population showed a risk of potentially decreasing slowly,
412 while the Croatian population would increase but with potentially dramatic changes in the
413 population structure with a lack of older males. Neither of these two outcomes would be desired by
414 either country. Seeing as both countries have adaptive management systems where quotas are
415 informed by annual monitoring it is unlikely that either country would allow such undesired
416 developments to appear without there being some reactions in terms of quota (e.g. since 2012
417 Croatia implemented higher quotas and management rules that aim to increase the proportion of
418 females in the bag). Furthermore, the assumption of no density dependence in our relatively simple
419 models would likely no longer apply under the rapid growth scenarios in Croatia. However, the
420 results do illustrate the impacts that the different policies are having on the overall population.

421 When viewed as a single population it appears that the different policies in effect even each other
422 out such that the overall population trend is positive with no larger changes in population structure.

423 The scenario that treats the population as a single unit has been realistic when considering
424 that most individuals are shot within a home range diameter of the border. There is also plenty of
425 evidence of transboundary movements of individuals from GPS and VHF collared animals [1634,35]
426 and from genetics studies [21]. The border effect is slightly asymmetric, with a higher proportion of
427 the Slovenian bears being influenced by cross-boundary issues than Croatia's. This is because of the
428 geographical alignment of bear habitat in the two countries. However, it must be remembered that
429 Croatia has an additional border with Bosnia and Herzegovina where bears are also hunted.
430 Unfortunately, due to an almost total lack of information about the status of the population part in
431 Bosnia and Herzegovina and its management, it was not possible to model the impacts. Another
432 potential effect of Slovenia's high harvest rates is that it slows the expansion of bears to the north,
433 which is necessary to ensure the longer-term viability of the reintroduced Alpine population of bears
434 in Italy and Austria [22,5049].

435 At the time of initiating this analysis, and for the period from which data was drawn, there
436 were no barriers to bear movement between Croatia and Slovenia. The summer of 2015 dramatically
437 changed this as the Slovenian government responded to the refugee crisis by building a fence along
438 the international border with Croatia. In its current form, there are apparently some openings that
439 allow bear movement. However, if the refugee crisis increases the fence could be extended over the
440 entire border between the countries and this would very likely cut the population into two halves
441 [20,21]. The result of this would be that the two countries could no longer count on their neighbours'
442 management to buffer the impacts of their national policies. For Slovenia, this implies that there will
443 be a need to kill fewer bears, and to show greater caution (and high precision) with management
444 because they are managing a smaller (and effectively isolated) population such that the role of
445 stochastic events becomes greater. For Croatia, it implies that they will need to increase their harvest
446 of females if they wish to prevent rapid population growth but at the same time decrease harvest of
447 older males. However, Croatia has the advantage of having a larger population with a high degree of
448 connectivity to the wider Dinaric population. In this context, our modelling scenarios provide an
449 illustration of the potential impacts of border security fencing. These impacts should provide
450 considerable weight when evaluating the legality of these hastily erected structures [51].

451 The objectives of pan-European legislative instruments such as the Bern Convention and the
452 Habitats Directive is to encourage countries to work together on conservation activities that cannot
453 be achieved in isolation. Unfortunately, neither instrument has formal mechanisms in place to
454 enforce this goal, apart from a set of guidelines for population-level management which were
455 introduced in 2008 [6]. However, Slovenia and Croatia since 2007 have initiated a series of meetings
456 between their respective management agencies and are taking steps to coordinate management.
457 Decisions are still made separately in each country but with a respect on annual reports from the
458 neighbouring country.

459 Although the vast majority of the human-induced mortality documented in this study was
460 under direct management control (through quotas) it is important to highlight the importance of
461 traffic induced mortality in both countries. Both countries have made dramatic investments in their
462 transport infrastructure (especially highways) in the last 25 years. The problem with bear mortality
463 has been highlighted for more than two decades [52,53]. In contrast to border security fencing, the
464 mortality and fragmentation impacts of transport infrastructure can be mitigated through the use of
465 green bridges and other crossing structures [54,55]. Unfortunately, there has not been a uniform
466 integration of such structures into highways and consequentially there will continue to be both
467 fragmentation and mortality effects on the population. The same applies to the illegal killing of bears.
468 Although there were only a few documented cases in our material [32], it represents an
469 underestimate of the total extent of the problem. Collecting such data is always very difficult. While
470 at present there is little evidence that the issue is widespread, management must show an
471 awareness of its potential to have dramatic impacts, e.g. [56] if public opinions [49] should change.

472 One of the weakest aspects in our models concerned the lack of local estimates of key
473 demographic parameters. Although basic data on COY and yearling rates could be obtained from the
474 feeding site counts (Supplemental file C) all other parameters had to be borrowed from Scandinavia.
475 Existing comparisons of data indicate that the two populations have broadly similar life-histories [16],
476 including when it comes to body mass and growth which is often a key determinant of other life
477 history traits [57]. Collecting demographic data requires a huge investment of resources using radio-
478 telemetry but is essential if locally adapted and precise parameter estimates are needed for
479 management. The sensitivity analysis (Table 3) identifies the key parameters with the highest impact
480 on the population. Unfortunately, data on cub/yearling survival and interbirth intervals are among
481 the most technically demanding of parameters to quantify. Newer indirect approaches using non-
482 invasive genetic data may provide good estimates of population size which was identified as a key
483 parameter [58]. While it is not unreasonable to assume that the Scandinavian data provides a general
484 idea of the approximate value of key parameters, there are some differences in habitats between the
485 two regions, both natural and anthropogenic. Probably the most important among the latter is the
486 widespread use of supplementary feeding in the Dinaric population, the effect of which is only poorly
487 understood [26,59,60].

488 However, important parameters such as inter-birth intervals and infanticidal rates will be
489 very hard to quantify, which will inevitably lead to uncertainties. The only way to deal with these is to
490 exercise caution in management interventions and to closely monitor population development and
491 adaptively respond hunting quotas to undesired developments.

492 5.1. Conclusions

493 Our study has a number of general conclusions valid for the conservation of large carnivores
494 and other wildlife globally. Firstly, it illustrated how two neighbouring countries can differ in the way
495 they manage a shared population. Secondly, our results showed how population connectivity can
496 even out such differences. Because this is due to a fortunate coincidence rather than careful planning
497 it underlines the need for countries sharing populations to formalize the ways they coordinate the
498 management of their shared responsibilities. Failure to do so could just as easily have led to mutual
499 disturbance of each other's goals [13]. The fact that most bears occurred close to the border also
500 underlines how crucial it is to cooperate in routine matters such as census to avoid double counting
501 individuals that occur on both sides of the border [10,11]. Finally, the data shows how dramatic the
502 impacts of constructed border security fencing can potentially have on the isolated segments that
503 remain within national borders if management regimes are not adjusted. Combined, these three
504 points underline how the fate of Europe's bear populations are influenced by socio-economic
505 (agricultural and transport policies and public attitudes) and political (at national and international
506 scales) factors far more than ecological factors.

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528 9. References

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687 10. Supplemental files

- 688 A. Challenges for transboundary management of a European brown bear population. Supplemental
689 file.
- 690 B. Mortality dataset for Slovenia and Croatia (2005-10)
- 691 C. Feeding sites count dataset for Slovenia (2005-10) and Croatia (2007-11)
- 692 D. R script for Croatia-Slovenia matrix model
- 693 E. R script for Croatia-Slovenia sensitivity analysis

HIGHLIGHTS

1. Majority of bears were removed within home range diameter from the state border
2. In Slovenia, 18.3% of the population was removed annually and in Croatia 8.9%
3. Croatian population increased with a change in structure and lack of older males
4. Slovenian population was stable or slightly decreased with a sustained structure
5. When combined, the different management policies in effect even each other out